

SOME THOUGHTS ON A POSSIBLE SYNTHETIC PETROL INDUSTRY IN INDIA*

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India's requirements of aviation and motor spirit are nearly 20 million gallons per month, but the indigenous production is only 1.5 million gallons. Apart from this, India needs very large quantities of kerosene (66,000 tons per month), high speed diesel, heavy diesel oil, light diesel oil and furnace oil for her various industries. The indigenous production of these is practically negligible. We produce 4,000 tons only of kerosene per month, 1,400 tons of high speed diesel, 2,000 tons of light diesel oil and 80 tons of furnace oil in the country. Therefore, the question of establishing synthetic petrol industry is of utmost importance.

At present, there are two types of synthesis possible :—

- (i) by the Fischer Tropsch process and
- (ii) by the hydrogenation of tar.

Which particular process for India would largely depend on the type of coal which would be available for the synthesis. It is clear that in order that the process may be an economical success, only inferior coal, which is available in abundance, can be used as a starting material. It was reported that bituminous coal of the Raniganj measures are available in abundance and it is therefore necessary to consider carefully the analysis and characteristics of this coal. For a preliminary investigation, three different coal samples were available. These samples were :—

- (a) Kajora coal from the area near Ondal
- (b) Dishergarh coal
- (c) Lower Jambad seam coal.

The coal analysed as follows.

TABLE I

Proximate analysis.

	(a) Kajora.	(b) Dishergarh.	(c) L.J.S.
Moisture (%)	4.8	3.2	5.2
Ash (%)	20.0	18.0	15.7
Fixed carbon (%)	48.0	45.8	48.9
Volatile matter (%)	29.2	33.0	30.2

Low temperature carbonisation.

	(a) Kajora.	(b) Dishergarh.	(c) L.J.S.
Carbonisation by Fischer test			
Tar (%)	11.2	11.4	11.4
Semi-coke (%)	71.4	71.0	69.8
Aqueous liquor (%)	4.0	5.8	6.0
Moisture (%)	4.8	3.2	5.2
Gas (%)	8.6	8.6	7.6

Calorific value.

	(a) Kajora.	(b) Dishergarh.	(c) L.J.S.
By conventional method			
Gross calorific value of raw coal (k.cal./kg.)	6.070	6.310	(— +)
Gross calorific value of coal, ash-free and moisture-free basis (k.cal./kg.)	8.090	8.000	(— +)

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Ash Fusing Point

The ash fusing point of coals (a) and (b) were determined by the Bunte-Baum method. The ashes show up to 1,300°C, only sintering and fuse at temperatures higher than 1,300°C.

From the above, it will seem that the coal is a relatively young bituminous coal. The percentage of volatile matter is about 40-50% related to ash-free and moisture-free basis. The fuel index i.e., the proportion of fixed carbon and volatile matter amounts to 1.3 to 1.6 and is therefore near the upper limit of bituminous coals. The lower Jambad Seam coal has a higher percentage of oxygen and fixed moisture and is therefore younger or oxidised by atmospheric influences. Contrary to accepted belief, we found Dishergarh and Kajora coal to be caking. The caking power originates from the portion of bright coal. The coal contains varying portions of bright and dull coal. To eliminate caking bright coal, separation of coal into these two constituents may be probably possible. A separation in the laboratory gave 35 to 40% of bright coal and 65 to 60% of dull coal. Cokes from Kajora and Dishergarh coal show that the vitrain-clarain substance is fused and swelled. Thus the bright coal which consists of vitrain and clarain seems to have perhaps sufficient caking properties for coking. Though L.J.S. coal yields, if crushed to 8mm. size and separated by heavy medium separation, about 25% of bright coal and 75% of dull coal, it does not cake. The lower Jambad coal therefore is gasifiable.

TABLE II

Lower Jambad Seam Coal

East Raniganj coal from field (S 682)

(a) Chemical and petrographic analyses.

	Total coal.	Bright coal.	Dull coal.
Moisture(%)	5.0	4.1	5.4
Ash (dry)(%)	18.6	6.1	22.4
Volatile matter (dry)	34.4	37.1	33.9
Ash-free and moisture-free coal :			
Volatile matter (%)	42.3	39.5	44.8
Fixed carbon (%)	57.7	60.5	55.2
Caking index	0	0	0
Density	—	1.333	1.437
Vitrain (%)	31.1	—	—
Clarain (%)	24.4	—	—
Durain (%)	3.0	—	—
Semi-fusain (%)	6.2	—	—
Fusain (%)	5.4	—	—
Bituminous shale	29.5	—	—
Gangue (%)	0.4	—	—

(b) Sink and float analyses.

Density range.	Portion.	Ash.
—1.28	3.6	1.5 %
1.28—1.30	5.9	2.7
1.30—1.35	10.4	6.3
1.35—1.40	24.4	13.3
1.40—1.45	11.7	16.8
1.45—1.50	15.0	20.5
1.50—1.60	18.2	27.1
1.60—1.90	10.2	39.9
More than 1.90	0.6	60.9

(c) Analyses of coal preparation products
(Heavy medium separation)

	Bright coal.	Dull coal.
Ash (%)	6.8	22.2
Carbon (%)	75.7	79.1
Hydrogen (%)	4.6	5.6
Nitrogen (%)	1.6	1.8
Sulphur (%)	0.9	1.0
Oxygen (% by diff.)	17.2	12.5
Gross calorific value (k.cal/kg.)	—	7,730
Net calorific value (")	—	7,428
Tar (%)	—	11.3

(d) Heavy medium separation of coal 8.1 mm. size

	Bright coal. Below 1.35	Dull coal. Above 1.35
Density	23.7	76.3
Percentage	6.9	22.0
Ash (%)	38.2	33.6
Volatilo matter, dry (%)	41.0	43.6
Volatilo matter, moisture-free and ash-free (%)	59.0	56.4
Fixed carbon (%)	1.347	1.485
Average density		

Summarising the results of the coal analyses, it may be pointed out :

The Raiganj measures hold a variety of different types of young bituminous coal with caking and non-caking character. Coal can be separated by suitable preparation into a more or less caking bright coal portion (containing vitrain and clarain) and a non-caking dull coal portion (consisting mainly of durain and bituminous shale).

Caking coals e.g., Kajora and Disherghar coals have caking properties which may exclude direct utilisation for gasification and Spuelgas carbonisation. Should it prove impracticable to separate bright and dull coal by proper mining, crushing to 8 mm. size and subsequent heavy-medium separation may be successfully applied to these types of coal, thus to separating them in bright coal, probably suitable for coking and non-caking dull coal for pressure gasification, as coal, small sized by preparation, makes gasification of Spuelgas carbonisation at atmospheric pressure difficult. The caking coals yield 35 to 40% of bright coal and 65 to 60% of dull coal.

Non-caking coal as Lower Jambad Seam coal can be gasified without any special preparation other than crushing and screening to eliminate dust.

The tar content of all types of Raiganj coal amounts to about eleven percent and as its recovery as by-product will be of fundamental importance for the total economy of the plant, immediate gasification of the coal combined with tar recovery will be the most useful process.

Modern gasification technique has developed the complete gasification of solid fuels by means of oxygen. There are five possible methods by which synthesis gas can be prepared :—

- (i) Koppers coal dust gasification
- (ii) Winkler coal gasification
- (iii) Water gas coke gasification
- (iv) Lurgi coal gasification
- (v) Reforming coke oven gas

After careful consideration, I have come to the conclusion that in India we should employ a process which would be based on hydrogenation of low temperature tar simultaneously with a Fischer-Tropsch synthesis. Therefore, the most ideal plant for India would be composed of a low temperature coal carbonisation plant and a tar hydrogenation plant. 50% of the required hydrogen can be produced by coal dust gasification (or any of the other processes found to be economically suitable) and 50% by tail gas and propane splitting.

Assuming an yield of about 20% below 1/4" size after the coal is crushed, we will require to handle 1.3 million tons of coal annually. The coal handling would include crushing to 3" and screening in 1" to 3" and 1/4" to 1" sizes as feed for the low temperature carbonisation. The sizes below 1/4" can be used for coal dust gasification and partly for generation of power.

The low temperature coal carbonisation plant would be required to produce 112,000 tons per year of tar and 700,000 tons per year of char. There is a market for the sale of 500,000 tons of the 1" to 3" char as domestic coke. The balance of 200,000 tons of smaller size can be consumed in a power generating plant.

The total required amount of hydrogen (98% purity) for hydrogenation would be 630,000 SCF per hour. 50% of the hydrogen would be produced by dust gasification and 50% by splitting of the hydrogenation off-gases. In the Koppers dust gasification process, it has been stated that the composition of the gas will be :—

Hydrogen	..	42%
Carbon monoxide	..	42%
Carbon dioxide	..	14.7%
H ₂ S	..	0.1%
Nitrogen	..	1.2%

In the splitting plant, the hydrogenation off-gas can be split over the catalyst by means of steam at high temperature. The split gas will have an ultimate composition of :—

Hydrogen	..	75.3%
Carbon monoxide	..	11.6%
Carbon dioxide	..	11.6%
Nitrogen	..	1.5%

The admixture of the split gas with the gas from the dust gasification plant can be designed to give a gas of the following analysis :—

Hydrogen	..	57.6%
Carbon monoxide	..	27.7%
Carbon dioxide	..	13.3%
Nitrogen	..	1.3%
H ₂ S	..	0.1%

The sulphurated hydrogen and other sulphur containing substances can be removed through iron oxide boxes. Carbon monoxide can be shifted to hydrogen and carbon dioxide by means of a two-stage shifting plant. The carbon dioxide can be removed with monoethanolamine, giving hydrogen of 98% purity. This hydrogen will have to be pressed to a pressure of about 10,000 to 10,500 psig. The process of conversion of tar to liquid fuels would follow the normal practice of hydrogenation by means of high pressure, temperature and catalyst.

In the feed preparation of the liquid phase, the bottom product of the liquid phase distillation can be mixed with the heavy oil let down product of the liquid phase.

Besides the liquid products, a certain amount of gaseous hydrocarbons (C₁-C₄) is formed in the liquid and vapour phases and can be released by depressuring the products in two steps and so forming a lean and rich off-gas. The greater part of the lean gas will be treated in the splitting plant. The rest of the lean gas can be used as fuel. The rich gases can be separated into methane, ethane, propane, *isobutane*, *n-butane*, *isopentane* and *n-pentane*. *isoPentane* can be added to aviation petrol and *n-pentane* to motor petrol. *n-Butane* can be isomerised to *isobutane*. Propane can be dehydrogenated to propylene. The propylene and *isobutane* can be reacted producing alkylate, which can go to the aviation petrol base.

Synthesis gas having carbon monoxide to hydrogen ratio of 1 : 2 by a suitable shifting

reaction can be reacted over an iron oxide-chromium oxide catalyst to give Fischer-Tropsch type of products.

The synthesis gas compressed to 300 lbs. sq. inch can be reacted over fluidised catalyst. In this catalytic reaction, large quantities of heat are released which according to modern tech. can be utilised for the production of steam.

In the fractionation of the hydrocarbons recovered from the recycle gas steam, the high boiling fractions can be recovered giving diesel oil and heavy residual oil. This latter can be sold directly or can be used as charging stock for an oil refinery cracking still.

The fluidised catalyst process has been in use on a very large scale in the U.S. for some years in the oil refinery industry. It has been tried out in a demonstration plant in California for Fischer-Tropsch synthesis.

As to the process steps comprising gas purification, CO conversion, CO₂ scrubbing and the fractionation of refining of the crude oil, all these are long established well known processes.

To summarise, my views are that we should attempt to produce aviation petrol and motor petrol in specific quantity relationship with diesel oil and fuel oil as co-product. A substantial quantity of low temperature char should also be produced for use as domestic fuel, so that the cost of production of synthetic fuel is minimised as far as possible. The best process for meeting the above requirements would be a combination of low temperature carbonisation on Raniganj coal to produce char for domestic fuel and tar for processing to produce aviation petrol. The tar will be subjected to high pressure hydrogenation for production of aviation and motor fuel. The char which is not sold for domestic use can be completely gasified (in conjunction with a certain amount of pulverised coal) to produce gas. This gas can be processed in a Fischer-Tropsch synthesis unit to produce a crude oil which can be refined to motor petrol, diesel oil and fuel oil.

The Lurgi process for low temperature carbonisation has been commercially used in Germany for many years. In this process, the evolved gases are continuously recycled to carbonise the raw coal which is charged in two separated sizes, namely, 1" to 3" and 1/4" to 1". The resultant char is screened and the 1" to 3" size is sold for domestic use. The minus 1" size can be used for direct production of synthesis gas and hydrogen. Tar and light oil are separated from the carbonisation gas and these are hydrogenated in the liquid phase and subsequently vapour phase using hydrogen generated in the gasification phase, in the presence of a suitable catalyst. This treatment results in crude aviation petrol which is then refined by distillation and dehydrogenation. As a by-product of value, about 1,800 tons of phenols can be recovered.

For the production of 70,000 tons of aviation petrol and 22,000 tons per year of motor fuel, 15,000 KW per hour and 500,000 lbs. of steam per hour would be needed to cater for electric power and process steam requirements, respectively.

An approximate idea of the capital cost will be as follows.

TABLE III

	Rs. crore		Rs. crore
Coal preparation ..	..	Distillation ..	.. 0.55 "
Low temp. carbonisation (including tar & light oil) and phenol recovery ..	.. 4.7 "	Rich gas recovery ..	.. 0.20 "
Coal dust gasification ..	.. 1.4 "	Propane dehydrogenation ..	.. 0.24 "
Oxygen plant ..	.. 0.58 "	Isomerisation ..	.. 0.07 "
Tail gas & propane splitting ..	.. 0.50 "	Alkylation ..	.. 0.47 "
Sulphur removal ..	.. 0.06 "	Tank Farm ..	.. 0.70 "
CO shifting ..	.. 0.22 "	Power Station ..	.. 3.10 "
CO ₂ scrubbing ..	.. 0.47 "	Refrigeration ..	.. 0.15 "
Raw gas & hydrogen compression ..	.. 0.96 "	Cooling water system ..	.. 0.14 "
Hydrogenation ..	.. 3.00 "	General facilities ..	.. 2.5 "
		Preparation of site ..	
		Total ..	.. 21.01 "

About 70% of the equipment can be procured from Europe and only about 30% will have to be procured from the U.S.A. and other hard currency areas.

Taking the average price of run-of-mine coal to be Rs. 11/- per ton and the selling price of coke to be Rs. 22/- per ton and the price of 1800 tons of phenols at Rs. 7,500/- per ton, the cost of manufacture of aviation petrol comes to nearly Rs. 1/4/- a gallon, while that of the motor petrol is slightly over a Rupee per gallon.

It would, therefore, seem that the production of synthetic petrol even under the present day conditions would not be an entirely uneconomical process.